

Synthetic Ester Lubricants : Pt. I-Synthesis and Properties of 2,2-Dialkyl-1,3-Propanediol Esters

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Two series of polyol esters using 2-methyl-2-*n*-propyl-1,3-propanediol and 2,2-diethyl-1,3-propanediol and straight chain monocarboxylic acids of C₅ - C₂₂ carbon number were prepared. Three synthetic fatty acid mixtures obtained by the oxidation of wax were also used to prepare the corresponding mixed esters of two diols. The composition and basic properties like density, R.I. and viscosities at 100°F were determined. The densities of the esters decreased with increasing C-number of the fatty acids while the refractive indices increased. The viscosities also increased with increasing chain lengths of acids. Presence of unsaturation in acid chain showed much higher viscosity than with the corresponding saturated acid.

SYNTHETIC esters are widely used as aviation engine oils and for several other specific purposes due to some excellent properties.

Two types of esters are of major commercial interest as lubricants¹⁻³ for use at low to moderate temperatures, the diesters of long chain monohydric alcohols and C₅ - C₁₀ dibasic acids and for higher temperature applications of the hindered esters of neopentyl-type alcohols and polyols condensed with monocarboxylic acids. The hindered esters have better thermal and oxidation stabilities as well as the viscosity temperature characteristics than the diesters. In these, the higher stability is due to the absence of hydrogen at the β-carbon to the alkoxy groups in the esters from neopentyl alcohols. Such esters have, therefore, found wide acceptance for use in high speed jet aircraft.

Several studies have been reported⁴⁻¹¹ in literature on hindered esters from substituted propanediols such as neopentyl glycol, 2-ethyl-2-butyl-1,3-propanediol, 2-methyl-2-ethyl-1,3-propanediol,

and cyclic diols like CH₂(CH₂)_nC(CH₂OH)₂ and evaluation of their properties relevant for lubricants. However, detailed studies are not known on the esters of 2-methyl-2-*n*-propyl-1,3-propanediol(I) and 2,2-diethyl-1,3-propanediol(II), which are commercially available. The synthesis and basic properties of two series of esters from these diols are reported here. These were prepared using monocarboxylic acids ranging from C₅ through C₂₂ saturated acids, oleic acid, and three synthetic fatty acid mixtures obtained by the oxidation of paraffin wax.

Experimental

Material used :

2-Methyl-2-*n*-propyl-1,3-propanediol was an analytical grade product of Riedel de Hann, West Germany.

2,2-Diethyl-1,3-propanediol was an analytical grade product of Fluka, Switzerland.

Fatty acids : C₅ to C₂₂ saturated acids and oleic acid were all commercial products and had purities over 98%. Wherever necessary, they were further purified by distillation.

Synthetic acids : Mixtures of synthetic fatty acids were the laboratory samples obtained from the wax oxidation laboratory of our Institute. These had the following characteristics :

Mixture A : Boiling range 99-120°/3 mm. The major components were C₇ and C₈ acids along with some C₆ and C₉ acids.

Mixture B : Boiling range 120-145°/2.5 mm. The major constituents were C₁₀ - C₁₂ acids with smaller amount of C₉ acid.

Mixture C : Boiling range 105-145°/1 mm, contained C₁₂ - C₁₅ acids, predominantly C₁₃ and C₁₄.

Complete GLC analyses of the methyl esters of these synthetic acid mixtures are given in Table 1.

Esterification : Esterification of the diols was carried out in a round-bottom flask fitted with a thermometer, a Dean and Stark receiver, and a reflux condenser.

A mixture of the alcohol and the acid, the latter 5% in excess of the stoichiometric ratio, was refluxed with a suitable solvent (benzene, toluene or xylene) in the presence of *p*-toluenesulphonic acid, approximately 0.5% of the reactants. The reaction

TABLE 1—GLC-ANALYSIS DATA OF THE THREE SYNTHETIC FATTY ACID MIXTURES (ANALYSED AS METHYL ESTERS, % OF TOTAL)

Acid	Mix. A	Mix. B	Mix. C
C ₅	1.0	—	—
C ₆	9.9	—	—
C ₇	32.5	—	—
C ₈	47.5	0.8	—
C ₉	8.1	8.9	—
C ₁₀	1.0	32.1	—
C ₁₁	—	36.2	1.3
C ₁₂	—	20.2	12.5
C ₁₃	—	0.8	50.6
C ₁₄	—	0.9	29.9
C ₁₅	—	0.1	3.9
C ₁₆	—	—	1.5
C ₁₇	—	—	0.3

time was less with the lower acids than that required for higher acids; this was observed from the formation of water collected in the receiver. Refluxing was continued till the water ceased to appear in the receiver. Use of toluene or xylene facilitated in

reducing the reaction time. The products obtained with these solvents were, however, slightly dark in colour. After the reaction, the product was cooled to room temperature and was thoroughly washed successively with water, 10% aqueous sodium bicarbonate, and water and dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate. The product was stripped off the solvent under reduced pressure.

The solvent-free product was finally passed over activated bauxite to make it free from the residual acid; the colour of the product also improved during this treatment. Product yields were 85-93%.

Elemental analysis, molecular weight, specific gravity (method IP 169/89), and refractive index and kinematic viscosity (method IP 71/66) of the esters are given in Tables 2 and 3.

Discussion

The esters of both the diols with saturated fatty acids (upto 16 carbon atoms) and those with mixed synthetic fatty acids were liquids at room

 TABLE 2—PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF THE ESTERS OF 2-METHYL-2-*n*-PROPYL-1,3-PROPANEDIOL

Sl. No.	Acid used for esterification	Carbon atoms in acid chain	Elemental Analysis				Molecular wt.		Refractive Index at 20°	Specific gravity at 20°	Viscosity at 100°F Cst.	Acid value (mg KOH/g)
			C%		H%		Calcd.	Found				
1.	Valeric	5	68.00	67.87	10.67	10.88	300.0	285.4	1.4386	0.9429	4.92	0.57
2.	Caproic	6	69.51	69.57	10.98	11.08	328.0	328.5	1.4409	0.9332	6.17	0.1
3.	Enanthic	7	70.79	70.89	11.23	11.24	356.0	348.2	1.4439	0.9265	7.50	Nil
4.	Caprylic	8	71.81	71.91	11.45	11.29	384.0	340.0	1.4466	0.9169	8.43	0.48
5.	Pelargonic	9	72.81	72.72	11.65	11.62	412.0	407.1	1.4488	0.9120	10.23	0.24
6.	Capric	10	73.36	73.38	11.81	11.91	440.0	441.4	1.4490	0.9088	13.42	Nil
7.	Lauric	12	75.00	74.52	12.09	12.07	496.0	500.8	1.4509	0.9026	18.97	1.13
8.	Myristic	14	76.08	75.69	12.32	12.21	552.0	572.7	1.4537	0.8962	25.15	1.09
9.	Palmitic	16	76.97	77.34	12.50	12.42	608.0	563.0	1.4578	0.8928	33.46	1.2
10.	Stearic	18	77.71	77.38	12.65	12.52	664.0	634.7	—	—	48.25	1.3
11.	Behenic	22	78.86	78	12.89	12.49	776.0	753.0	—	—	—	2.5
12.	Oleic	18	78.18	78.48	12.12	12.44	660.0	653.8	1.4668	0.9026	71.50	0.98
13.	Mixture A	7-9	71.32	71.03	11.35	11.31	370.0	388.0	1.4475	0.9210	8.15	0.38
14.	Mixture B	10-12	74.12	74.48	11.92	11.92	458.2	452.0	1.4529	0.9120	13.72	0.88
15.	Mixture C	12-15	75.69	75.69	12.24	12.11	530.40	576.6	1.4565	0.9107	22.11	1.41

TABLE 3—PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF THE ESTERS OF 2,2-DIETHYL-1,3-PROPANEDIOL

Sl. No.	Acid used for esterification	Carbon atoms in acid chain	Elemental Analysis				Molecular wt.		Refractive Index at 20°	Specific gravity at 20°	Viscosity at 100°F Cst.	Acid values (mg KOH/g)
			C%		H%		Calcd.	Found				
1.	Valeric	5	68.00	67.72	10.67	10.50	300.0	315.1	1.4429	0.9523	5.31	2.24
2.	Caproic	6	69.51	69.21	10.98	10.67	328.0	295.0	1.4460	0.9444	6.90	0.56
3.	Enanthic	7	70.79	70.63	11.23	11.11	356.0	330.0	1.4484	0.9391	8.35	0.93
4.	Caprylic	8	71.81	71.55	11.45	11.40	384.0	364.0	1.4492	0.9315	9.63	1.72
5.	Pelargonic	9	72.81	72.65	11.65	11.42	412.0	380.5	1.4512	0.9235	10.78	2.23
6.	Capric	10	73.36	73.02	11.81	11.50	440.0	423.3	1.4515	0.9183	11.74	0.1
7.	Lauric	12	75.00	74.55	12.09	12.00	496.0	469.0	1.4543	0.9094	18.70	0.19
8.	Myristic	14	76.08	75.68	12.32	12.13	552.0	523.0	1.4555	0.9048	24.67	0.20
9.	Palmitic	16	76.97	76.54	12.50	12.30	608.0	587.1	1.4685	0.9025	32.78	0.5
10.	Stearic	18	77.71	77.40	12.65	12.56	664.0	653.2	—	—	44.65	0.33
11.	Behenic	22	78.86	78.76	12.89	12.60	776.0	755.5	—	—	—	1.01
12.	Oleic	18	78.18	77.82	12.12	11.98	660.0	650.0	1.4699	—	69.54	1.5
13.	Mixture A	7-9	71.31	71.63	11.35	11.31	369.2	400.0	1.4494	0.9329	9.89	0.61
14.	Mixture B	10-12	74.12	73.91	11.92	11.82	458.4	476.3	1.4539	0.9204	14.69	1.02
15.	Mixture C	12-15	75.69	75.38	12.24	12.15	530.4	523.7	1.4566	0.9108	21.99	0.98

temperature while the esters from still higher acids were semi solid or wax-like solids.

The specific gravity of the esters in both the series continuously decreased with increasing carbon number of the acid used ; the decrease was relatively more in the case of lower acids. The specific gravity of the diol(II) esters was always higher than that of the corresponding esters from Diol (I).

The refractive indices of the esters with saturated acids in each series generally increased with the increasing carbon number of the acid group. However, the R.I. increment appeared to be minimum between the C₉ (pelargonic) and C₁₀ (capric) acid esters. The refractive indices of the symmetrical diol(II) esters were always higher than those of the corresponding esters from Diol(I). Both the diols have the same number of carbon atoms but differ only in the branching at the quaternary carbon atom ; it is symmetrical in diol(II) and unsymmetrical in diol(I). The intermolecular cohesive energy is expected to be larger for symmetrical structure and is perhaps responsible for this small but significant difference in these two properties.

Viscosity is an important property of lubricants. For high speed jet lubricants the viscosity specified at 100°F is 25 Cst minimum. In the two series of esters studied, the viscosity regularly increased with increasing carbon chain of the acid. The viscosities of the esters of the two diols with the same acid were, however, almost similar. The esters of the mixed synthetic acids were also comparable with those of pure acids of corresponding carbon numbers. The esters from myristic acid (C₁₄) onward had viscosities 25 Cst and above. But among them only myristic and palmitic (C₁₆) acid

esters are liquids. With lower acid esters the desired viscosity can possibly be achieved through blending with suitable high viscosity fluids.

It was noteworthy that the oleic acid esters had much higher viscosities than the esters from the corresponding saturated stearic acid (C₁₈) esters.

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